

Course program: Transportation of passengers. Support and assistance to passengers with reduced mobility in transport

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Abstract: This course is developed to implement state policy on ensuring the accessibility of infrastructure and services for persons with disabilities and other people with reduced mobility. For directors, senior executives, managers, professionals involved in the provision of services of air, road, rail, river transport and underground transportation.

Keywords: Course program, transportation of passengers, passengers of reduced mobility, transportation.

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1. Explanatory memorandum

Transport is an essential area of everyday life. The development and implementation of accessible transport policies and services contributes to improving the lives of people, including people with disabilities; it is a prerequisite for achieving equal opportunities and including all population groups in the social life.

The concept of "accessible transport" can be considered, firstly, as the availability of the vehicle itself, secondly, as the transport infrastructure, equipped according to the current legislation and needs of people with disabilities and other population groups with reduced mobility, and thirdly, as the provision of quality services to passengers.

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) requires the State Party to take all appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to transportation and services both in urban and in rural areas. The ensuring of these principles directly depends on the professional training of specialists and decision makers.

The ideology of the course is based on the socio-legal model of disability and the recognition that disability is the result of "the interaction that occurs between people with disabilities and obstacles in relationships and in the environment".

Launching the course "Transportation of passengers. Support and assistance to passengers with reduced mobility in transport" will promote the implementation of international commitments undertaken by Ukraine on training experts on disability, providing quality services in the transport

sector as well as promote the implementation in transport policy when forming an inclusive approach based on human rights.

This course provides a systematic review of key issues related to the legal framework governing the provision of transport services, defining requirements for transport operators, drivers, vehicles and their equipment, rights and obligations of passengers as well as provides an opportunity to get people with reduced mobility acquainted with the rules of assistance and support providing.

The course can be used for training and retraining of specialists, managers, who work in the field of providing motor transport services.

Implementation of the course is crucial because of the need of students to obtain and enhance previously acquired knowledge and skills in assistance to people with reduced mobility, to study legislation and to meet regulatory compliance in the field of passenger transportation services, to resolve issues of accessibility, reasonable accommodation, transportation security, assistance to passengers with reduced mobility, occupational health and safety in their determined activities.

Goal of the course: to acquire basic knowledge in providing transport services to people with disabilities and reduced mobility, in universal design, reasonable accommodation, existing methods of assistance to people with reduced mobility and of ethics in communications with this group of passengers, to implement changes in services for people with reduced mobility.

2. Course objectives

To systematize knowledge about:

- concepts of "disability", "reduced mobility", "accessibility", "services for all";
- principles of universal design and "reasonable accommodation" as well as their practicing in the sector of transport services;
- security of services provision for population groups with reduced mobility;
- existing methods of support and services provision to ;
- best practices of providing "transport services for all" by domestic and foreign transport operators and service sector entities.

To form skills (abilities) that concern to:

- providing services and assistance to people with reduced mobility;
- working in a team;
- communicating with persons with certain functional disorders;
- using of "reasonable accommodation" during the provision of transport services.

To ensure a close connection between both the theoretical and practical components of the training course.

The duration of the training course "Transportation of passengers. Support and assistance to passengers with reduced mobility" is 18 hours.

This course is developed to implement:

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities; the Laws of Ukraine "On Road Transport", "On the Fundamentals of Social Security of the Disabled People of Ukraine"; the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of June 4, 2003 No 863 "On Approval of the Program for the Unhindered Access of People with Disabilities to Housing and Public Facilities"; the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of August 1, 2012 No. 706 "On Approval Of the State Target Program "National Action Plan to Implement the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" until 2020"; the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of December 3, 2008 No. 1081 "On approval of the Procedure establishing a tender process for passenger transportation on the public bus route" (in particular, item 8) of paragraph 29 of the Section "Submission of documents for participation in the tender": "8) a list of vehicles adapted for the carriage of persons with disabilities that are offered for work on the bus route or written information about their absence; { item 8 of the paragraph 29 as amended by the Resolution No. 1310 (1310-2009-p) of 03.12.2009}"); the Order of the Ministry of Transport and Communications of Ukraine No.1196 of 27.12.2006 "On Approval of Rules for transportation of passengers, baggage, cargo and mail by railway transport of Ukraine (in particular, Section 38 "Special aspects in transportation of persons with disabilities"); the Order of the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine No 411 of 24.07.2012 "About the Program on creation of proper conditions for the access of people with disabilities to the objects of road transport and tourism infrastructure as

well as postal services”; the Regulation (EC) No 181/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 February 2011 concerning the rights of passengers in bus and coach transport and amending Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004.

This course is recommended for all Training Centers of special training for directors, managers, escort services, flight attendants, employees of airports, bus stations, railway stations involved in the provision of services in transport (hereinafter - Training centers), which received in due course a Certificate for the relevant areas of training.

A typical curriculum includes theoretical and practical training of students.

3. CURRICULUM

Table 1: Curriculum for the course "Transportation of passengers. Support and assistance to passengers with reduced mobility in transport"

Curricula	Curricula	Curricula	
		Curricula	Including
		Lectures	Practical's
I. Basic course			
1	Fundamentals of international and national laws governing the accessibility of transport services for passengers with reduced mobility	2	-
2	Accessibility of the transport sector for people with reduced mobility	2	
3	Concept of universal design and reasonable accommodation	2	
	Total:	6	-
II. Special training			
4	Organizational features of transportation of passengers with reduced mobility	2	-
5	Support for passengers with reduced mobility	2	-
	Total:	6	-
III. Practical training			
6	Support for passengers with locomotor disorders. Transferring techniques for persons using wheelchairs		4
7	Support for passengers with visual impairment		2
8	Support for passengers with mental disabilities and hearing impairment		1
	Testing	1	
	Total:	6	
	Grand Total:	18	

4. COURSE SYLLABUS

4.1. Basic course

Topic 1. Fundamentals of international and national law governing the availability of transport services for passengers with reduced mobility

The UN Convention on the rights of persons with disabilities presents new approaches to issues of accessibility of transport and transport services. Concepts of "disability", "reduced mobility", "passengers with reduced mobility". Ukrainian law and international agreements regulating transportation accessibility for passengers with disabilities. Tasks and functions of state regulation and monitoring of passenger transport activities. Legislative regulation of passenger transportation services. The rights and obligations of carriers and passengers.

Recommended literature list:

1. UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 61/106 of 13.12.2006 (the Convention was ratified by the Law of Ukraine No. 1767-VI of 16.12.2009).

2. World Program of Action Concerning Disabled Persons: UN General Assembly Resolution No 37/52 of 03.12.1982.

3. Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 48/96 of 20.12.1993.

4. Council of Europe Action Plan to promote the rights and full participation of people with disabilities in society: improving the quality of life of people with disabilities in Europe 2006-2015: Recommendation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Council of Europe Rec(2006)5 of 05.04.2006.

5. Law of Ukraine "On Road Traffic".

6. Law of Ukraine "On Railway Transport".

7. Law of Ukraine "On Urban Electric Transport".

8. Law of Ukraine "On Transport".

9. Decree of the President of Ukraine of 18.12.07 № 1228/2007 "On additional urgent measures to create favorable conditions for the life of people with disabilities".

10. Action plan to create a barrier-free life environment for people with disabilities and other population groups with reduced mobility for 2009-2015 "Barrier-free Ukraine", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet Ministers of Ukraine No. 784 of 29.07.09.

11. Action plan related to solving some problems with social protection of disabled persons, approved by the Ordinance of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1460 of 03.12.09.

Theme 2. Accessibility of the transport sector for people with reduced mobility

Accessibility as one of the main factors guaranteeing the rights of persons with disabilities. Accessibility in various spheres of life. Concept of "transport accessibility". Requirements for the accessibility of transport infrastructure. State building code requirements governing the accessibility of transport infrastructure. Modern logistics of accessible vehicles, services and infrastructure: international and Ukrainian experience. Special aspects in passenger services providing on different modes of transport (automobile, air, rail, river, underground).

Recommended literature list:

1. UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 61/106 of 13.12.2006 (the Convention was ratified by the Law of Ukraine No. 1767-VI of 16.12.2009).

2. Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 48/96 of 20.12.1993.

3. Consolidated Resolution on Road Traffic: Resolution of Working Party on Road Traffic Safety of Inland Transport Committee of Economic Commission for Europe. Access: ECE/TRANS/WP.1/123.

4. Council of Europe Action Plan to promote the rights and full participation of people with disabilities in society: improving the quality of life of people with disabilities in Europe 2006-2015: Recommendation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Council of Europe Rec (2006) 5 of 05.04.2006.

5. Action plan to create a barrier-free life environment for people with disabilities and other population groups with reduced mobility for 2009-2015 "Barrier-free Ukraine", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet Ministers of Ukraine No. 784 of 29.07.09.

6. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 18.02.1997 No. 176 "On Approval of the Rules for the provision of passenger motor vehicle services".

7. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 03.12.2008 No. 1081 "On approval of the Procedure establishing a tender process for passenger transportation on the public bus route".

8. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 03.12.2009 No. 1342 "On Approval of Vehicle Parking Rules".

9. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 11.09.2011 No. 560 "On Approval of the Procedure for Approval of Construction Projects and Their Examination, and on repealing some of the Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine".

10 Order of the Ministry of Infrastructure of 27.09.2010 No. 700 "On approval of the Regulation of the bus stations activities", registering by the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine on 11.11.2010 by No. 1068/18363.

11. State Construction Norms ДБН В.2.2-17:2006 Accessibility of houses and facilities for people with reduced mobility (ДБН В.2.2-17:2006 Доступність будинків і споруд для маломобільних груп населення).

12. State Standard of Ukraine ДСТУ-Н Б В.2.2-31:2011 Guidance on arrangement of residential housing and public facilities with elements of accessibility for persons with visual and hearing impairments" (ДСТУ-Н Б В.2.2-31:2011 Настанова з облаштування будинків і споруд громадського призначення елементами доступності для осіб з вадами зору та слуху).

13. Accessibility and universal design: guidance manual / Ed. by Baida L.Y., Krasnyukova-Enns O.V. - K., 2013. - 128 p.

14. Disability and Society: guidance manual / Ed. by Baida L.Y., Krasnyukova-Enns O.V. / Authors: Baida L.Y., Krasnyukova-Enns O.V., Burov S.Y., Azin V.O., Grybalsky Y.V., Nayda Y.M. - K. 2012. – 216 p.

Theme 3. The concept of universal design and reasonable accommodation

Concept of "universal design". History of establishing the "universal design" concept. International and national legislation and regulations on universal design. Principles of the universal design. Social advantages of universal design. Modern researches and developments in the field of universal design and reasonable accommodation, their practical application in transport sector. Concept of "smart device".

Recommended literature list:

1. UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 61/106 of 13.12.2006 (the Convention was ratified by the Law of Ukraine No. 1767-VI of 16.12.2009).

2. Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 48/96 of 20.12.1993.

3. Achieving full participation through Universal Design: Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe CM/Rec(2009)8 of 21.10.2009.

4. On the introduction of the principles of universal design into the curricula of all occupations working on the built environment: Resolution ResAP(2001)1 (Resolution Tomar) of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe of 15.02.2001.

5. Council of Europe Action Plan to promote the rights and full participation of people with disabilities in society: improving the quality of life of people with disabilities in Europe 2006-2015: Recommendation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Council of Europe Rec(2006)5 of 05.04.2006.

6. Access to residential housing and public facilities for people with disabilities: Methodical manual // Edition V. VGSP0 "National Assembly of Invalids of Ukraine". - K., 2011.

7. Accessibility and universal design: guidance manual / Ed. by Baida L.Y., Krasnyukova-Enns O.V.-K., 2013. - 128 p.

8. Disability and Society: guidance manual / Ed. by Baida L.Y., Krasnyukova-Enns O.V. / Authors: Baida L.Y., Krasnyukova-Enns O.V., Burov S.Y., Azin V.O., Grybalsky Y.V., Nayda Y.M. - K. 2012. – 216 p.

Useful links:

Universal design: Site. Access <http://ud.org.ua/>

4.2. Special training

Theme 4 Special aspects of organization of transportation of passengers with reduced mobility

Passengers with reduced mobility, special aspects in providing transport services due to the different medical conditions of persons with disabilities. Requirements to vehicles and technical devices facilitating access for passengers with reduced mobility. International experience in implementing the principles of accessibility in vehicle construction. Specifics in accompanying passengers with reduced mobility during services providing in transport sector.

Recommended literature list:

1. UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: UN General Assembly Resolution No 61/106 of 13.12.2006 (the Convention was ratified by the Law of Ukraine No. 1767-VI of 16.12.2009).
2. Law of Ukraine "On Railway Transport".
3. Action plan to create a barrier-free life environment for people with disabilities and other population groups with reduced mobility for 2009-2015 "Barrier-free Ukraine", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet Ministers of Ukraine No. 784 of 29.07.09.
4. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 18.02.1997 No. 176 "On Approval of the Rules for the provision of passenger motor vehicle services".
5. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 03.12.2008 No. 1081 "On approval of the Procedure establishing a tender process for passenger transportation on the public bus route".
6. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 03.12.2009 No. 1310 "Tender process for passenger transportation on the public bus route".
7. Order of the Ministry of Transport and Communications of Ukraine No. 1196 of 27.12.2006 "On Approval of Rules for transportation of passengers, baggage, cargo and mail by railway transport of Ukraine".
8. Order of the Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine No 411 of 24.07.2012 "About the Program on creation of proper conditions for the access of people with disabilities to the objects of road transport and tourism infrastructure as well as postal services". Access: <https://www.zakon-i-normativ.info/index.php/component/lica/?href=0&view=text&base=1&id=1236025&menu=1>
9. UN Regulation No. 107: Annex 8 "Accommodation and accessibility for passengers with reduced mobility".
10. DSTU 7013:2009 Specialized buses for carrying schoolchildren. Technical requirements (ДСТУ 7013:2009 Автобуси спеціалізовані для перевезення школярів. Технічні вимоги).
11. DSTU EN 12312-14: 2010 Aircraft ground support equipment. Specific requirements. Section 14. Disabled/incapacitated passenger boarding vehicles» (EN 12312-14: 2006 + A1: 2009, IDT) (ДСТУ EN 12312-14:2010 Авіаційна наземна техніка. Спеціальні вимоги. Частина 14. Транспорт для посадки інвалідів та осіб з обмеженими фізичними можливостями (EN 12312-14:2006+A1:2009, IDT))
12. DSTU GOST 30478: 2006 Buses for carrying persons with disabilities. General technical requirements (ДСТУ ГОСТ 30478:2006 Автобуси для перевезення інвалідів. Загальні технічні вимоги")
13. DSTU GOST 30795: 2009 Passenger rail locomotive traction of main railways of the railways 1520. Technical requirements for the transportation of persons with disabilities (GOST 30795-2001, IDT) (ДСТУ ГОСТ 30795:2009 Вагони пасажирські локомотивної тяги магістральних залізниць колії 1520. Технічні вимоги щодо перевезення інвалідів (ГОСТ 30795-2001, IDT)).

Theme 5. Support for passengers with reduced mobility

Support for passengers with reduced mobility. Ethics of communications, means and methods of providing support, information, services to passengers with reduced mobility. Predicting and understanding customer needs. Practice in using compensatory and supporting facilities for certain

types of transport. International experience in implementing the principles of accessibility in the vehicle design.

Recommended literature list, useful links:

1. Access to residential housing and public facilities for people with disabilities: Methodical manual // Edition V. VGSPU "National Assembly of Invalids of Ukraine". - K., 2011.
2. Lessons in specific etiquette: Video. Access: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XBkcIU8yHa8>
3. Service sector for all: Training course // Authors: Volodymyr Azin, Larysa Bayda, Yaroslav Hrybalskyy, Olga Krasnyukova-Enns, Yuliya Naida. - K., 2011 - p. 77 Access: <http://gar.org.ua/publikatsiji>

4.3. Practical training

Theme 6. Support for passengers with locomotor disorders. Transferring techniques for persons using wheelchairs

Determination of the concepts of "support" and "assistance / transfer of passengers with locomotor disorders". Addressing post-traumatic complications of people with locomotor disorders during the assistance services providing in transport (occurrence of pressure ulcers, use of incontinence devices, spastic manifestations, osteoporosis, etc.).

Special aspects in accompanying passengers with locomotor disorders on the territory and in the premises of transport undertakings as well as in the salons of vehicles (bus, rail car, aircraft cabin).

Methods of transferring persons with locomotor disorders on and out of wheelchairs (for ramp, for steps and for cabin) indoors and inside a vehicle without using assistive devices.

Ways to support and provide assistance to passengers using wheelchairs at dealing with curbs, ramps, escalators and stairs.

Addressing situations of risk and humanitarian emergencies in the organization of services for passengers with locomotor disorders (safety and security, evacuation).

Recommended literature list, helpful links:

1. Verkeyk Julian. "On the road again": Guide for care spinal cord-injured patients. - K.: "Ros". - 2010.
2. Indolev Leo. "Life in a wheelchair" (rus). - M.: 2001 - 446 p.
3. Indolev Leo. Wheelchairs and how to use them: Film (rus) / All Russian Society of Disabled People. - 2000.
4. Bedsores. Preventing and treating: Information material / Lviv regional organization of active rehabilitation of disabled people "Stimulus". - 2003.
5. Bedsores. Prevention and treatment: Video Guide. / Media Center "Rozmai". - 2011.
6. Support and help: Step by Step: Manual / Bayda L.Y., Azin V.A. // MO "Children's cultural and educational center" - K., 2012. - Page 28 - 68 Access: <http://gar.org.ua/publikatsiji>
7. Service sector for all: Training course // Authors: Volodymyr Azin, Larysa Bayda, Yaroslav Hrybalskyy, Olga Krasnyukova-Enns, Yuliya Naida. - K., 2011 - p. 77 Access: <http://gar.org.ua/publikatsiji>
8. Yes, you can!: Guidebook to self-care for people with spinal cord injury / NRHOI "Center for Independent Living "Finist" Access: <http://naiu.org.ua/zhittya-pislya-travmi-spinnogo-mozku-pidtrimka-doglyad-ta-dopomoga/>
9. Technique and means for transferring people in a wheelchair: Film / Lviv regional organization of active rehabilitation of disabled people "Stimulus" - 2003.

Theme 7. Support for passengers with visual impairment

Methods of providing assistance and support for passengers with visual impairment inside the premises of transport enterprises, on the surrounding area and in the cabin of a vehicle. Accompanying several persons with visual impairment by only one companion. Supporting people with multiple impairments in transport. Guide-dogs and their role in the lives of people with visual impairment, external features, recommendations for communication with dogs by the transportation sector employees.

Addressing situations of risk and humanitarian emergencies in the organization of services for passengers with visual impairments (security, evacuation).

Recommended literature list, helpful links:

1. Service sector for all: Training course // Authors: Volodymyr Azin, Larysa Bayda, Yaroslav Hrybalskyy, Olga Krasyukova-Enns, Yuliya Naida. - K., 2011 - p. 77 Access: <http://gar.org.ua/publikatsiji>
2. Lessons in specific etiquette: Video // Vinnycia non-governmental organization of young people with disabilities "Harmony". Access: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XBkcIU8yHa8>

Theme 8. Support for passengers with mental disabilities and hearing impairment

Special aspects in providing support services to passengers with mental disabilities during the transport services providing. Application of icons. Application of simplified language.

Special aspects in providing support services to passengers with hearing impairment in transport.

Addressing situations of risk and humanitarian emergencies in the organization of services for passengers with hearing impairment and mental disorders (security, evacuation).

Recommended literature list, helpful links:

1. Lessons in specific etiquette: Video // Vinnycia non-governmental organization of young people with disabilities "Harmony". Access: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XBkcIU8yHa8>

5. Questions for total control

1. Comment on the meaning of "disability" concept according to the UN Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities.
2. Comment on the meaning of "accessibility" concept according to the UN Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities.
3. What models of disability, on your mind, are the most appropriate for modern requirements to social policy in Ukraine?
4. Who, according to the relevant regulatory practices in Ukraine, are referred to people with reduced mobility? According to what documents?
5. Define concept of "universal design" and its principles.
6. Define concept of "reasonable accommodation" according to the UN Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities. Give examples.
7. What is the difference between the concepts of "universal design", "accessibility", "reasonable accommodation"?
8. What includes the concept of "transport accessibility"?
9. What medical conditions are basic to form accessible transport services for passengers with reduced mobility? Give examples.
10. What compensatory and assistive devices may be used for transport to ensure easy access to transportation services for passengers with reduced mobility?
11. Explain the definition of "body field zone" and "common area for comfortable reach" for passengers with regard to their medical conditions.
12. What are the main requirements during support providing to passengers with locomotor disorders?
13. What are the main requirements during support providing to passengers with visual impairment?
14. What are the main requirements during support providing to passengers with hearing impairment?
15. What are the main requirements during support providing to passengers with cognitive impairment?
16. What is the purpose and use of the international symbol of accessibility?

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://jsdtl.sciview.net> and <http://naiu.org.ua/>.

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